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CONTENTS

03 Editorial

News

05 Banking News

08 RBI News

10 Legal Cases

12 Industry News

14 Housing Finance News

16 Mutual Fund News

17 Export Import News

19 News Flash

20 People on the Move

21 Press Release

Features

50 RBI Circular

52 Case Study

53 RBI Update

55 Ready Reckoner

56 Profile

Articles

29 Record Performance of Fmcgs Companies
in India and abroad

Dr. C. Vethirajan & Mr. K. Muneeswaran

36 Growth trend in ATMs in
Commercial Banks in India

Dr. I. Maria Jesili & Mrs. N. Sowbrniga Devi

43 Recent Trends and Development of
E-Banking: Indian Perspective

Mr. Pema Lama & Ms. Suranjana Saha

RECORD PERFORMANCE OF FMCGS COMPANIES IN INDIA AND ABROAD

Introduction

FMCG industry, alternatively called as CPG (Consumer packaged goods) industry primarily deals with the production, distribution and marketing of consumer packaged goods. These are products that have a quick turnover, and relatively low cost. Consumers generally put less thought into the purchase of FMCG than they do for other products.

Though the absolute profit made on FMCG products is relatively small, they generally sell in large numbers and so the cumulative profit on such products can be large. Some of the prime activities of FMCG industry are selling, marketing, financing, purchasing, etc. The industry also engaged in operations, supply chain, production and general management.

FMCG industry provides a wide range of consumables and accordingly the amount of money circulated against FMCG products is also very high. The competition among FMCG manufacturers is also growing and as a result of this, investment in industry is also increasing, specifically in India, where FMCG industry is regarded as the fourth largest sector with total market size of US\$13.1 billion.

FMCG Sector in India is estimated to grow 60% by 2010. FMCG industry provides a wide range of consumables and accordingly the amount of money circulated against FMCG products is also very high. The competition among FMCG manufacturers is also growing and as a result of this, investment in FMCG industry is also increasing, specifically in India, where FMCG

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industry is regarded as the fourth largest sector with total market size of US\$13.1 billion. FMCG Sector in India is estimated to grow 60% by 2010. FMCG industry is regarded as the largest sector in New Zealand which accounts for 5% of Gross Domestic Product (GDP). At present, urban India accounts for 66% of total FMCG consumption, with rural India accounting for the remaining 34%.

However, rural India accounts for more than 40% consumption in major FMCG categories such as personal care, fabric care, and hot beverages. In urban areas, home and personal care category, including skin care, household care and feminine hygiene, will keep growing at relatively attractive rates. Within the foods segment, it is estimated that processed foods, bakery, and dairy are long-term growth categories in both rural and urban areas.

Historical Background

Organized manufacturing in the Indian FMCG sector started early in the 20th century. Most FMCG companies were multinationals having started mainly as trading companies. However, as the Indian market started becoming more attractive, these companies started to set up manufacturing facilities in India. In the past, major FMCG companies like ITC, HLL, Cadbury, and Nestle ruled the roost with hardly any competition and the markets had a high entry barrier.

These companies could therefore price their products at a premium. However, with the advent of globalization the sector has opened up. It is no longer a seller's market but a buyer's market where the consumer has a wide range of choice, due to which FMCG companies have been forced to slug it out for their market share. Consequently their margins have taken a hit.

Different Components of the FMCG Market

Household Care

Household Care products include bath soaps and detergents.

Bath soaps. The market size for soaps is estimated at Rs 83 billion, comprising the premium, economy and popular. The penetration level of soaps is 92 per cent. They are available in 5 million retail stores, of which 75 per cent are in the rural areas. Hindustan Unilever Limited (HUL) is the leader

with a market share of 53 per cent; Godrej occupies second position with a market share of 10 per cent. With increase in disposable incomes, rural demand is expected to increase because consumers are moving up towards premium products.

Detergents : The size of the detergent market is estimated at Rs.120 billion. Small unorganised players account for a major share of the detergent market. In washing powders, HUL is the leading company with 38 per cent of the market share. Other major players are Nirma, Henkel, and Proctor & Gamble.

Personal care : Personal care products include skin care, hair care and oral care products.

Skin care : The total skin care market is estimated at Rs. 34 billion. This market is at a nascent stage in India. The penetration level of this segment in India is around 20 per cent. With changing lifestyles, increase in disposable incomes, greater product choice and availability, people are becoming more aware about personal grooming. Major players in this segment are HUL with a market share of 54 per cent, followed by Cavin Kare with a market share of 12 per cent, and Godrej with a market share of 3 per cent.

Hair care : The hair care market in India is estimated at Rs. 38 billion, including hair oils, shampoos, hair colourants, conditioners and hair gels. Marico is the leader in hair oil segment with a market share of 83 per cent; Dabur occupies second position at 17 per cent.

Shampoos : The Indian shampoo market is estimated at Rs. 27 billion. It has a penetration level of only 13 per cent. Sachets make up 40 per cent of the total shampoo sales. It has a low penetration level even in metros. Again, the

market is dominated by HUL with around 47 per cent of market share; P&G occupies second position with a market share of around 23 per cent.

Oral care : The oral care market can be segmented into toothpastes (60 per cent), toothpowder (23 per cent) and toothbrushes (17 per cent). The total toothpaste market is estimated at Rs. 35 billion. The penetration level of toothpowder and toothpaste in urban areas is three times that of rural areas. This segment is dominated by Colgate-Palmolive with a market share of 49 per cent, while HUL occupies second position with a market share of 30 per cent. In the toothpowder market, Colgate and Dabur are major players.

Food & beverages : This market includes tea and coffee as well.

Food : The food category in FMCG is gaining popularity with a string of launches by HUL, ITC, Godrej and others. This category has 18 major brands aggregating Rs. 46 billion. Nestle and Amul slug it out in the milk powder segment. The food category has also seen innovations like softies in ice creams, ready-to-eat rice by HUL, and pizzas by Godrej Pillsbury.

Tea : The tea market is dominated by unorganised players, who control over 50 per cent of the market. The leading branded tea players are HUL and Tata Tea.

Coffee : More than 50 per cent of the market is dominated by loose, unbranded coffee. Major players in this segment are Nestle, HUL and Tata Coffee.

Fast moving consumer goods in Asia

Asia's rising affluence will drive the growth for FMCG firms over the next several years. In 2011, aggregate demand for consumer goods in Asia has remained strong, and demand for soaps and cleansers is forecast to have grown more strongly than previously expected in India, Hong Kong and China, at 11.1%, 8.6% and 12% respectively, against earlier forecasts of 9%, 5% and 10.1%. India's rapidly-growing middle class, with annual household incomes of US\$3,000 - 5,000 is becoming increasingly brand-conscious and aware of the importance of personal grooming.

The market for cosmetics, toiletries and other personal care items is concentrated, with a few well-known brands dominating sales of shampoos, hair conditioners, make-up, fragrances and personal hygiene products.

Growth in demand for most of these products is expected to be rapid in 2011-15, leaving scope for new companies to make inroads into the current market leader's dominance men's grooming products, and such as skin lightening creams, deodorants, facials cleansers and so on is an area that is showing steady growth.

Retail and Consumer Product Sector in Asia - An Out Look India often throws up surprising sales strategy successes. For example Amway, an American direct sales retailer, has become one of India's largest consumer goods companies since the government allowed it to start selling its products door-to-door. However, the markets will get tougher as consumer tastes evolve rapidly based on rising incomes, more companies enter the fray and established market leader step up their game, for example Nestle has been in India for almost a century.

Now it is moving to keep pace with the market. Five years ago it undertook "Project Epicure" under which it made 1,500 visits to Indian homes, rich and poor, to see how people cook and eat. On 30 July 2011, it reported a 20% increase in total sales to Rs.17.63 billion (US\$ \$394 million) and a 9% rise in its net profit for the second Quarter to Rs.2.14 billion (US\$ 47.8 million). It is planning to invest US\$ 450 million to double its capacity. Emerging as future growth markets based on the rise of the young, urban, increasingly affluent Indian consumer.

TABLE 1
Record performance of Retail and Consumer product sector in India & Abroad

(In Percentage)

Sl. No	Territory	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	Rank
1.	Asia and Australia	4.3	6.5	5.2	5.9	7.0	5.9	5.8	5.3	III
2.	China	13.3	18.6	3.2	12.0	12.7	9.7	9.3	7.3	II
3.	Hong Kong	3.9	7.0	8.7	8.6	6.8	3.7	3.4	3.0	V
4.	India	10.2	16.6	14.1	11.1	9.9	10.5	9.8	9.8	I
5.	Japan	-0.8	0.6	3.5	-0.6	2.4	1.5	1.4	1.0	VI
6.	Taiwan	-0.8	2.0	5.0	5.5	5.4	4.1	4.8	4.7	IV

Source : Economist Intelligence Unit. Figures for 2011 onwards are forecasts.

Table 1 shows that India is the first place for consumer product sector among all the countries. It is found that in India there has substantially increase in consumer product sector followed by China (7.3%), Asia (5.3%), Taiwan (4.7%), Hong Kong (3.0%) and Japan (1.0%) the place of second, third, fourth, fifth and sixth respectively achieved consumer product sector. China has from 16.3% in 2008 to 18.6% in 2009 but there was a declined trend from 9.7% in 2013 to 9.3% in 2014. Consumer product sector in Taiwan has considerable increase from 4.1% in 2013 to 4.8% in 2014.

It is developing products suited for the Indian market and even express product development in India to both Asian and Eastern European countries. The real anticipates that almost 70 % of its launches in India in 2011-12 will be if products that are locally developed, including skincare product for men.

FMCG Sector - Indian Scenario

Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) can be defined as packed goods that are consumed or sold at regular and small intervals. The prices of the FMCG are relatively less and profits earned through such sales are more volume based.

The organized FMCG retailing in India is a new concept and is fast catching up in urban and semi-urban India. The FMCG Sector in India has witnessed a range of recent developments. Tax deductions on various items, rise in the penetration levels and per capita consumption are some of the major developments in FMCG.

Approximately 200 million people are expected to become the consumers of processed and packaged foods by the year 2010. The major activities of the food-processing sector are permitted 100% foreign equity or 100% NRI and Overseas

Corporate Bodies (OCB) investment to meet the rising demand of the consumers. In the year 2012, the recent developments in FMCG, it is assumed that the consumption of the FMCG products will have a satisfactorily growth with the rising income level of Indian populace in both the rural and urban areas. The market size of the Indian FMCG Sector is expected to reach USD 33.4 billion by the year 2015.

The Indian government has declared several tax sops for the FMCG sector in India. It has emphasized on the infrastructural developments in the same. The consumption of health and personal care products in FMCG sector has increased in the recent past with rise in disposable income especially among the early stages group in India.

A few of the FMCG product are Toiletries, Soaps and detergents. Cleaning and disinfecting agents, Cosmetics, Non-durables and Pharmaceuticals.

Further, the packaged food products and drinks are also sold under the FMCG, since these items are consumed or bought at regular intervals. Furthermore, recently the electronic items like mobile phones, MP3 players, external hard drives, etc, which has less life owing to its technological development, has also been brought under the gamut of FMCG sector.

With this back ground information, the researcher has presented the detail of top most FMCG companies operating in India with various types of products marketed in India in Table 2.

TABLE 2
Top Most FMCG Companies Operating in India

Sl. No	Company	Segments
1.	HUL	Personal Care, Food Products, Household Care, Baby Care, Fabric Care
2.	Amul India	Food Beverage Products
3.	Nestle India	Food Beverage Products
4.	ITC	Personal Care, Food Products
5.	Britannia	Food Products
6.	Dabur	Personal Care, Food Products, Household Care
7.	Marico Industries	Personal Care, Household Care, Food Products
8.	CSK Consumer	Personal Care, Food Products
9.	Cadbury India	Food Products
10.	Colgate Palmolive	Personal Care, Oral Care
11.	Procter and Gable	Personal Care, Household Care, Baby Care, Fabric Care
12.	Godrej	Personal Care, Fabric Care

Source : Relevant Company Websites, IBEF Report, March 2010.

Further the researcher has analysed the advertising expenditure for FMCG Companies and trend and growth of performance and sales of FMCG by leading FMCG

Companies in India for the period 2009 to 2012. The results of which are presented in Table 3.

TABLE 3
Advertising Expenditure for Leadings FMCGs Companies (Rs.in Crore)

Sl. No	FMCG Companies	2011-2012	2012-2013	Growth (%)
1.	Hindustan Unilever	2,635	3,232	23
2.	Godrej Consumer	603	964	60
3.	Dabur India	660	837	27
4.	Bharti Airtel	559	599	7
5.	Marico	426	598	40
6.	Britannia	420	534	27
7.	GSK Consumer	437	496	14
8.	Colgate Palmolive	412	490	19
9.	Idea Cellular	421	453	8
10.	Nestle India	356	396	11

Source : Business Line 17th April 2014.

Table 3 exhibits that advertising expenditure for Hindustan Unilever has from Rs.2635 Crore in 2011-2012 to Rs.3,232 Crore in 2012-2013. The growth rate was 23%. The advertising expenditure for Godrej consumer increased from Rs.603 Crore in 2011-2012 to Rs.964 Crore in 2012-13. The average growth rate of the advertising expenditure from 2011-12 to 2012-13 was 60%. The average growth rate of Britannia from 2011-12 to 2012-13 was 27% the average growth rate and Nestle India for the period 2011-12 to 2012-13 works out to be 11%.

TABLE 4
Performance and Sales of FMCGs by Leading FMCGs Companies in India

(Million in US\$)

Sl. No	FMCG Companies		Year				CAGR %
			2009	2010	2011	2012	
1.	Hindustan Unilever	Amount	12,019	17,764	19,691	22,116	2.56
		Percentage of Change	-	47.80	10.85	12.32	
2.	Britannia	Amount	3,421	3,773	4,605	5,485	17.04
		Percentage of Change	-	10.29	22.05	19.11	

3.	Nestle India	Amount	4,324	5,129	6,255	7,491	20.10
		Percentage of Change	-	18.62	21.95	19.76	
4.	Dabur India	Amount	2,805	3,390	4,077	5,305	23.66
		Percentage of Change	-	20.86	20.27	30.12	
5.	Godrej Consumer	Amount	1,393	2,041	3,643	4,866	51.73
		Percentage of Change	-	46.52	78.49	33.57	
6.	Colgate Palmolive	Amount	1,695	1,962	2,221	2,693	16.69
		Percentage of Change	-	15.75	13.20	21.25	
7.	Marico	Amount	2,388	2,661	3,128	4,008	18.84
		Percentage of Change	-	11.43	17.55	28.13	
8.	CSK Consumer Health Care	Amount	1,542	1,922	2,306	2,686	20.32
		Percentage of Change	-	24.64	19.98	16.48	

Source : Report "India FMCG Industry" India Food Guide, Edelweiss, Dinoida Capital Advisors, September 2012.

It may be observed from the Table 4 shows that the compound of annual growth rate (CAGR) of sales by Godrej and for the period 2009 to 2012 works out to be 51.73%. The performance and sales & Dabur India has substantial increase from 2,805 million US\$ in 2009 to 5305 million US\$ in 2012. The CAGR and Dabour India sales performance from 2009 to 2012 was 23.66%. The CAGR and CSK consumer Health care for the period 2009 to 2012 works out to be 20.32%.

FMCG Market in Tamil Nadu

The Indian state of Tamil Nadu is one of the most vibrant and happening place in terms of business activities. FMCG Market in Tamil Nadu has huge scopes with the rise in the income of the general people.

The state has made major progress in the Information Technology sector along with Automobile and Telecommunication sectors. Tamil Nadu houses big companies like TCS, IBM, Cognizant, Wipro, Nokia in the IT and Telecommunication sector. Tamil Nadu is also the home for several automobile manufacturing units.

Furthermore, the state has become one of the major designations for quality technical education in India. All these factors along with the fact that its capital - Chennai is an also a metro city has propelled the growth of the city. The state is one Oise largest producers of ago-products like tea, coffee, sandalwood, cashew, coconut and spices, rice,

which have facilitated the growth of food industry in the state.

The state of Tamil Nadu has a number of important cities like Chennai, Coimbatore, Sivakasi, Trichy, Erode, and Kodaikanal, Ooty etc, which has made great progress- Industrialization of Tamilnadu, has led to the further development of consumerism in the state.

This increased consumerism facilitated growth of the FMCG market in Tamil Nadu. The FMCG industry in Tamil Nadu is shaping up under the umbrella of organized sector and it is distinctly classified into four different segments like Food and Beverage industry, Cleaning, Disinfectants and Home Care, Personal care and Electronics.

TABLE 5
FMCG Market in Tamil Nadu - Major
FMCG Companies

Nestle	ITC	Mother Dairy	Jyothy Laboratories
Kellogg's	MTR	Amul India	Godrej Sara Lee
Pepsi	Perfetti	Gits Food Products Pvt. Ltd	Johnson & Johnson
Coca Cola	Tata Tea	Kwality Walls	Himalaya Health Care
Uni Lever	Parrys Confectionary	Vadilal Ice Cream	Modi Revlon
Cadbury India	Venkey's	Goodricke Chicken	Cavin Care
Parle	Goodricke	Smith Kline Becham	Lakme
Heinz	Nilgiris	Reckit Benckiser	L'Oreal
Lotus Herbals	Shahnaz Hussai	Hobibs	Procter and Gamble
LG	Samsung	Sony	Phillips
Videocon	Electrolux	Whirlpool	Kelvinator
Godrej	IFB	TCL	Haier
Panasonic	Motorola	Nokia	Sony Erickson

Source : Business Maps of India.com

FMCGS - Future Prospects of India

Fast-moving consumer goods (FMCGs) are products that are sold quickly at a relatively low cost. They are popularly referred to as consumer packaged goods. The most common things in the list are toilet soaps, detergents,

shampoos, and toothpastes, shaving products, shoe polish, packaged foodstuff and household accessories. The term even extends to certain electronic goods. These items are meant for daily or frequent consumption.

A major portion of the monthly budget of each household is reserved for FMCG products. The volume of money circulated in the economy due to FMCG products is very high, as the number of consumers for such products is very high.

The Indian FMCG industry began to shape during the last 50-odd years. The FMCG sector is a cornerstone of the Indian economy, touching every aspect of human life. The Indian FMCG market is divided between the organized sector and the unorganized sector. Unlike the US market for FMCGs, which is dominated by a handful of global players, India's Rs 460-billion FMCG market remains highly fragmented with roughly half the market being dominated by unbranded, un-pack-aged, home-made products. This presents a tremendous opportunity for marketers of branded products to convert consumers to buy branded products. FMCGs typically require a wide distribution network and are sold directly to the consumers.

Summary

The improved economic situation of both the rural and urban consumers has helped FMCG companies to further expand their market to the hinterlands of the country. It is the fourth largest sector in India, creating employment for more than 3 million people in the country. Marketers will need to evolve new strategies to connect and communicate with a more aware and unreserved consumer than ever before.

With this, product and brand development cycles will need to undergo a dramatic change. FMCG Company can change the consumer's mindset and offer new generation products. FMCG producers should understand these challenges and tune their strategies accordingly will surely be the winners in the years to come taking advantage of this economic boom for FMCGs in the rural sector of India.

References

References has been taken from various sources. It has not been listed here due to space constraint.